

Gender STI

D3.5 European Observatory on Gender in STI. Terms of Reference.

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LIST OF ABBREVIATIONS

AC	Associated Countries
CoP	Community of Practice
DG RTD	Directorate General for Research and Innovation
EC	European Commission
ERA	European Research Area
EU	European Union
GEP	Gender Equality Plan
LAB	Gender STI Co-Design Lab
LAC	Latin America and the Caribbean
MS	Member States
MSCA	Marie Skłodowska Curie Actions
NCP	National Contact Point
NGO	Non-Governmental Organisation
REA	European Research Executive Agency
RFO	Research Funding Organisation
RPO	Research Performing Organisation
RTO	Research and Technology Organisation
R&I	Research and Innovation
STI	Science, Technology and Innovation

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

A core element of the Gender STI project is the establishment of the European Observatory on Gender in STI (Science, Technology and Innovation), which will benefit policy debate on gender equality matters in STI and international cooperation. The Observatory is unique of its kind in Europe and will serve as a hub for gender equality in STI dialogues, incorporating all knowledge and materials resulting from the project and other gender initiatives supporting gender equality in international cooperation in STI.

Under the leadership of the Gender STI consortium, the Observatory will become the think tank for the Gender STI Community of Practice connecting all organisations interested in supporting gender mainstreaming in STI to foster collaboration and exchange of ideas and experiences.

The primary objective of the Observatory is to serve as a comprehensive and up-to-date source of information about Gender Equality implementation in STI dialogues with third countries.

The Observatory is accessible from the [project website](#). The initial structure of the Observatory comprises four key areas: Gender Equality in international STI dialogues; Co-Design Labs & Gender Equality Solutions; Gender STI Community of Practice and Resources.

The Gender STI project members are in the process of identifying, gathering and populating the Observatory sections to be operational by the end of October 2022. It includes the results of the mapping on gender equality in bilateral and multilateral agreements, alongside Co-design Labs prototypes and the Community of Practice workspace. Additionally, the observatory provides access to a wide range of resources from the Gender STI project and other projects and initiatives that support gender equality. Resources include scientific reports, policy briefs, surveys, training modules, comparative analysis, recommendations, infographics and visualizations, among others. The content will be updated regularly until the end of the project and beyond.

This report (Deliverable D3.5) presents the Terms of Reference of the European Observatory on Gender in STI, which outlines the purpose, activities and operation of the Observatory. It includes the following operational elements:

- Section 1 introduces the objectives, scope and target audience of the European Observatory on Gender in STI.
- Section 2 describes the Observatory's structure including principal components and categories of information.
- Section 3 outlines the observatory's governance, including the organisation and resources.
- Section 4 presents the conclusion and next steps.

1. INTRODUCTION

The European Observatory on Gender in STI is at the core of the Gender STI project and aims to act as a hub for the most comprehensive and up-to-date information on gender equality in STI. It will serve to advance the integration of the gender perspective in STI dialogues between Europe and third countries.

The Observatory has been designed to create a network between different sectors and stakeholders, which can generate and disseminate knowledge, thereby supporting effective decision-making, priority-setting, complement gender investigations or initiatives as well as implementing gender equality in STI dialogues and international cooperation in research and innovation.

The Observatory seeks to:

- Create a deeper understanding of gender equality in bilateral and multilateral STI dialogues.
- Promote and raise awareness on gender equality in STI dialogues.
- Bring together lived experiences, academic and non-academic, interdisciplinary and cross-sector contributions, to exchange and amplify ideas, evidence and expertise.
- Transfer knowledge and outcomes on gender equality in STI to stakeholder groups that can use the information.
- Disseminate Gender STI project's results, including the mapping of gender equality in bilateral and multilateral agreements in STI; prototypes and recommendations to integrate the gender perspective in STI; as well as resources, such as reports and policy briefs resulting from the Gender STI project and other EU-funded projects or initiatives
- Generate a think tank space, through the Gender STI Community of Practice, to facilitate interaction, debate and exchange of ideas between relevant stakeholders from Europe and third countries
- Create synergies with other EU-funded projects and initiatives.

The Observatory will benefit relevant stakeholder groups, including STI policy makers in Europe and in third countries, the gender research community or National Contact Points (NCP) networks, among others, as described below under the target audience section.

Additionally, the Observatory will provide a valuable entry point to data search, high-level ownership on gender reporting, and provides a window of opportunity for greater decision-making towards the achievement of gender equality and women's empowerment on STI international dialogues. It also aims to become an important tool for decision-making on negotiation, composition, operationalization and monitoring of international agreements in STI.

These Terms of Reference are a non-binding working document intended to evolve as the Observatory matures through the increasing involvement of the Gender STI partners.

1.1 Scope

The European Observatory on Gender in STI is the first of its kind tool in Europe and will provide a centralized hub for knowledge sharing and resources on gender equality in STI dialogues with third countries. The Observatory will provide access to data, information, analytics, lessons learned, methods, tools, programmes and initiatives on gender equality in STI international dialogues, among others. All these inputs shall be governed by the general principle of an open data policy.

The Observatory will leverage the expertise of the Gender STI project partners in gender equality, international cooperation in STI and policy dialogues, as well as their outreach channels to enhance the impact that the Observatory have at both European and international levels.

1.2 Potential users

The Observatory will focus on the following target groups:

- **STI policy makers in the European Union Member States (MS) and Associated Countries (AC), and third countries:** This group includes policy makers, such as the European Commission Directorate General for Research and Innovation (EC DG RTD), the European Research Executive Agency (REA), government bodies and institutions focused on gender issues in EU MS and AC. It also encompasses European and third country stakeholders and actors involved in STI bilateral and multilateral agreements, such as Ministries of Foreign Affairs, Ministries of Science and Technology, Funding Agencies, Research Funding Organisations, international cooperation agencies, etc.
- **Scientific and research community:** The scientific and research community involves research and scientific organisations, Universities, Research Performing Organisations (RPOs), Research and Technology Organisations (RTOs), including researchers in EU-funded projects as well as national projects and initiatives. The Observatory, through the Gender STI project, is well connected to the partners from sister projects that have shared their results in the resource section of the Observatory. That's the case of ACT-GenPORT, GENDERACTION, GE Academy, CALIPER, SUPERA, SPEAR, CALIPER, and GEECCO, among others.
- **STI Funding Organizations:** they finance and support STI projects of universities, research centres and companies through various funding programmes. These Organizations could benefit of solutions to assess gender and inclusivity in funding terms.
- **ERAC-related groups on gender equality in STI and international cooperation:** These groups are an important target as they advise the Council, the European Commission and EU Member States in European Research Area (ERA) priority areas such as gender equality and gender mainstreaming in research (priority 4) and international cooperation (priority 6).
- **High level group on gender mainstreaming:** This group plays a key role for the EU gender equality agenda, including in the formulation, programming and implementation of the EU Gender Equality Pact. It helps the Presidencies and the Commission to identify gender equality subjects and priorities which are of political relevance.

- **NCP networks in Europe and in third country partners:** The Observatory will also target the National Contact Points for Horizon Europe in Europe and third country partners such as MSCA-NET, Net4SocietyHE, and the Latin America and the Caribbean NCP Network (LAC NCP Network).
- **Industry leaders and innovators:** This group includes leaders at private technology companies, entrepreneurs, startups, think tanks, innovators and many others.
- **Civil Society Organisations:** This group includes charities, development non-governmental organisations (NGOs), community groups, professional associations, social movements and advocacy groups. They are key actors to promote gender equality in research and innovation, articulate the needs and interest of citizens and mobilize constituencies.

These groups receive the latest information through the “European Observatory on Gender in STI” newsletter, keeping them informed about the knowledge and materials on gender equality matters in STI and dialogues with third countries.

2. STRUCTURE OF THE OBSERVATORY

The Observatory is accessible from the [Gender STI website](#). It is organized in four sections:

1. Gender Equality in international STI dialogues
2. Co-Design Labs & Gender Equality Solutions
3. Gender STI Community of Practice
4. Resources

Figure 1: Website of the European Observatory on Gender in STI

2.1 Gender Equality in international STI dialogues

This section will introduce highlights of gender equality in international STI dialogues based on international data collection and analysis. It will serve decision-makers and researchers who are interested in insights in international STI dialogues.

First, this section will offer for example, the results of the mapping carried out by the Gender STI project, which includes the analysis of more than 500 bilateral and multilateral agreements between EU Member States, Associated Countries and third countries. The mapping determines how gender equality was taken into account and promoted in these agreements, identifying the main actors in STI dialogues.

Second, the section will offer data visualisations based on big data exercise that focuses on women participation in specific field of research, and main findings of international interview and survey data.

This section will include:

- Mapping of Gender Equality in Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements.
- Benchmarking on gender equality in STI dialogues
- Survey data on Gender Equality Implementation in STI Bilateral and Multilateral Agreements.
- Insights from stakeholders on gender inequalities in STI agreements
- Data visualization.

2.2 Co-Design Labs & Gender Equality Solutions

The Gender STI Co-Design Labs engaged STI stakeholders in a dynamic mix of workshops, demonstrations and guided hands-on teamwork based on design thinking principles. The Co-Design Labs facilitate the development of common solutions for three forefront challenges facing women in STI, which are at the core of the work performed by the Gender STI project: Gender equality in scientific careers; Gender balance in decision making bodies and positions; and Integration of the gender dimension in research and innovation content.

This section of the Observatory will include:

- Co-Design Labs Reports.
- Methodology Handbook on the Gender STI Co-Design Labs.
- Latest news about prototypes' development.

2.3 Gender STI Community of Practice

This Gender STI Community of Practice (CoP) will be the driver of the European Observatory on Gender in STI. The CoP will act as a multi-stakeholder collaboration platform for knowledge exchange on the integration of the gender perspective in STI dialogues and international cooperation between Europe and third countries. The members of the CoP serve as ambassadors promoting good practices and informed reflections on current trends of gender equality in STI and related topics such as, gender equality in scientific careers, gender balance in decision making and the integration of the gender dimension in Research and Innovation content.

This section will include:

- Goals and Mission
- Get to know our members
- Collaborative space

2.4 Resources

The resources provided by the Observatory will include information and materials about different Gender STI topics, work areas as well as research studies gathered from diverse projects and initiatives by stakeholders in Europe and third countries.

In addition to the results produced by the Gender STI project, we have contacted 23 sister projects and invited them to share their results, including reports, surveys, policy briefs, GEPs, videos, training modules, infographics, gender analysis tools and other materials, which are featured at the Observatory resources section.

The resources' page is organized in five categories to facilitate navigation through the page:

1. Gender Content in STI.
2. Gender Equality in Scientific Careers.
3. Gender Equality in R&I International Cooperation.
4. Gender Equality Plans.
5. Gender Equality Policies.

Users can also search by keywords.

Figure 2: Categories of Resources' page

Additionally, a section for Data resources is shown at the bottom page.

Figure 3: Data resources

3. GOVERNANCE

3.1 Organisation

The Observatory will be composed of a Steering Committee, acting as the decision-making body and a Secretariat that will coordinate the planning and implementation of the Observatory and will act as the executive body.

The Steering Committee will consist of senior representatives from the Gender STI partners, up to a maximum of 18 members, including members from Europe and from third countries involved in the project. The involvement of the Steering Committee members will be based on their experience and balance of expertise across academia, policy and private sector.

This group may also involve, on an ad hoc basis, people beyond the Gender STI project, such as stakeholders from other gender initiatives, in order to gain additional expertise and to provide new resources to the Observatory.

The Secretariat will be initially chaired by Inmark assisted by two Gender STI partners.

Responsibilities of the Steering Committee members

- Contribute to feed content to the Observatory.
- Commit to regular attendance at meetings and contribute to the agenda items.
- Disseminate and promote the Observatory in Europe and Third Countries.
- Explore the pathway for sustainability of the Observatory.
- Promote the Observatory as a hub for the integration of the gender perspective in STI dialogues with third countries.

Responsibilities of the Secretariat:

- Provide leadership in their day-to-day role.
- Schedule regular meetings.
- Select and provide specific content to the Observatory.
- Promote the Observatory as a hub for the integration of the gender perspective in STI dialogues with third countries.
- Monitor the gender dimension and inclusivity in the daily work of the Observatory

In the framework of the Gender STI project, Inmark will be responsible for updating and maintenance of the Observatory webpage in order to continue building the Observatory's reputation and promoting its resources through the project social media accounts.

3.2 Memorandum of Understanding

With a view to the long-term sustainability of the Observatory, the project partners confirm their deep commitment and high sense of responsibility to support the success of the Observatory established under the Gender STI project. To this end, the project participants agree to sign a Memorandum of Understanding (MoU) by the end of the project. The MoU is intended to express project participants' full

engagement, dedication and expertise to assure the Observatory sustainability beyond the project.

3.3 *Time involved*

After the end of the project, the Observatory will work on a voluntary basis, keeping in mind that the partners committed to keep the Observatory rolling will play an active role in its sustainability. The foreseen workload of the partners involved is estimated to be about a few hours per month. Furthermore, it is expected that this work should also be part of members' own projects or organisations' entailing events participation, active dissemination and other collaboration activities related to the promotion of gender mainstreaming in STI.

3.4 *Frequency and format of meetings*

- The Steering Committee will meet at least twice a year
- The Secretariat will meet every 2 months.
- It may also convene (either in its entirety or an agreed sub-set of group members) to advise on extraordinary, emerging matters throughout the year where these do not coincide with a scheduled meeting, and/or members may be asked to contribute to the process outside of the meetings on a purely voluntary basis.
- The Steering Committee and the Secretariat will convene virtual meetings through teleconference, video conference or other virtual communication/collaboration facilities or platforms.

4. CONCLUSION AND NEXT STEPS

Gender STI will create and launch the European Observatory on Gender in STI that will serve as a hub connecting all organisations and initiatives interested in supporting gender equality in international cooperation in STI.

The Observatory will incorporate all knowledge and materials resulting from the project as well as from other related projects and initiatives in Europe and third countries; and thus, it will benefit policy debate on gender equality matters in STI and international cooperation.

Through the Gender STI project, we have made initial contact with 23 sister projects asking them to identify and share potential resources for the Observatory as well as to invite them to join the Community of Practice.

It is intended that following the conclusion of the project, the Observatory will continue as a permanent, self-sustaining initiative, supported by the Gender STI project partners.

The next step is to establish the Steering Committee and Secretariat of the Observatory and draft the MoU to engage the project participants and to assure the Observatory sustainability beyond the project.

Then, we will continue creating a deeper understanding and awareness of the European Observatory on Gender in STI, promoting its objectives and benefits to the target audience. By developing this understanding among potential users, they will be able to clearly identify why the observatory is relevant to them or their work. Raising awareness of the Observatory and the importance of investigating the state of gender equality in STI dialogues with third countries is crucial. This will lay the groundwork for future communication and dissemination about the Observatory's progress and thus, for the use of the Observatory by different stakeholder groups able to provide information/data.

We believe that the Observatory will be a valuable reference to implement the inclusion of the gender equality perspective in STI dialogues with third countries.